

The Templum and the Liver of Piacenza in the works by Deecke, Körte, Vander Meer, Aveni and Romano

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The Liver of Piacenza is an Etruscan bronze artifact found in 1877. It is a life-sized model of a sheep's liver engraved with Etruscan inscriptions. It is dated to the late 2nd century BC, when the Piacenza region was under Latin domination. The liver is subdivided into sections, inscribed with names of individual Etruscan deities, suitable for performing haruspicy as hepatoscopy. The rim of this bronze artifact is divided into 16 sections, and therefore the liver had been supposed to represent a model of the sky, with the 16 sections as "dwelling places" of deities. For this reason, after its discovery, the object was supposed to represent a templum. Here we consider literature about the liver as a templum.

Introduction

To understand the importance of the Liver of Piacenza, let us consider what we can find told in the Enciclopedia Italiana, 1932, about the Etruscans' religion. The Enciclopedia entry tells us that the Latin writers had been impressed by the fact that the Etruscans arranged their divine world in a hierarchy. At the top we have the triad of Tinia (Jupiter), Uni (Juno) and Menrva (Minerva). About the importance of the triad, it is noted that, according to Etruscan discipline, the towns that did not possess three gates and three temples (or a tripartite temple) dedicated to the triad were not considered true cities. The triad in turn became part of an ennead to which the task of hurling thunderbolts was delegated. Varro knows of a council of twelve gods (dei consentes) who give advice to Tinia on hurling thunderbolts and of a second council of gods, of which neither is known, nor the name nor the number nor the figure (dei involuti), who advises and contributes to the thunderbolts that have destructive effects. The other deities outside of the triad can be grouped as follows, according to their Greek, Italic, or purely Etruscan origin. They are of Greek conceptual origin: Fufluns (Dionysus), Sethlans (Hephaestus), Turms (Hermes), Turan (Aphrodite); in conceptual origin and name: Aplu (Apollo), Artume (Artemis), Hercle (Heracles), Aita (Hades), Phersipnei (Persephone). They are of Italian origin: Maris (Mars), Nethuns (Neptune), Menrva (Minerva), Usil (Sun), Vesuna; and more especially Latin: Uni (Juno), Ani (Janus), Selvans (Silvanus), Satre (Saturn), Vetis (Veiove), Mae (Maio). They are Etruscan and of unknown interpretation: Cilens, Cvlalp, Ethauôva, Letham, Tecum, Thuflltha, Tluscv.

The rules of Etruscan discipline regulated every important act of public and private life, both in peace and in war, thus constituting a true legal code. Its main characteristic consisted in being a divinatory genre, defined by Cicero as "artificial", that is, it sought the supernatural response for the contingent case in completely external elements, based on the meticulous application of special acts and the observation of certain phenomena. The divine will could be investigated above all in lightning, in the flight of birds, in extraordinary events of all sorts, celestial and terrestrial, in the livers of sacrificed animals, so that the haruspicy constituted the fundamental part of the Etruscan discipline, and from it the priest, to whom the entire ritual was entrusted, was called haruspex: the corresponding Etruscan term seems to be *trutnvt*, which occurs in a bilingual inscription from Pesaro, referable to a haruspex perhaps coming from Tarquinia. The main task of the haruspicy was precisely the *extispicio*, i.e. the examination of the viscera of animals and especially the liver (of sheep), of which there were models for the teaching of this doctrine, one of the which, in bronze, is preserved in the Civic Museum of Piacenza.

The Enciclopedia Italiana tells that, in 1932, there was still much discussion about the precise value and meaning of this object (discovered in 1877), which was also considered a magical amulet, but according to the generally accepted interpretation, it referred to a special hepatoscopy which could be called "astrological": in fact the division of the flat surface into sixteen marginal sectors, in each of which the name of a deity is engraved, should be related to the division into equal numbers of sectors of the celestial vault, in each of which a different deity dominates, whose will is manifested through thunderbolts: the office of the *haruspex* is precisely that of establishing the precise point of the sky from which the thunderbolt (*manubiae*) comes, to interpret the divine will. We can also see, on this front side, other names engraved internally, within subdivisions of various shapes, for which complicated hypotheses have been put forward, and three elevations - one pyramidal, one conical, one globular - in which some scholars wanted to see, respectively, the correspondence with sky, sun and earth. In the convex rear part, only two names can be read: *usils* "of the sun" and *tivs* "of the moon". The Piacenza bronze has also been called "augural templum", as it depicts the sky, and "mundus", as it gives an image of the universe. The interpretation was aided by a very curious and variously understood passage by Marziano Capella, who in *De nuptiis Mercurii et Philologiae* divides the sky between 16 divinities, whose names find some correspondence with those engraved on the Etruscan bronze. The hypothesis therefore seems well founded, that the liver represents a microcosm reflecting the image of the macrocosm, giving us the visual representation of the complex divine system and the order of the universe. However, the bronze cannot be dated before the century III a. C.; therefore, in any case, it represents a very advanced stage of a special branch of Etruscan discipline.

What we reported above is the information we can find in the Enciclopedia Italiana, 1932.

Before discussing the liver, let us consider what is a "templum".

Templum (Nettleship, 1889)

The templum is "A square space or region marked out in the sky or on the earth by the *augures*, in which to look for signs. A templum, when on the earth, is not synonymous with *aedes sacra*, although it often happened that an *aedes sacra* was also a templum. The templum is only the space, not the building and again even the space is not *sacrum* until it has been consecrated by the pontifices. On the other hand, a building may be *sacra* and yet not a templum. Of the templum marked out in the sky and on the earth by the *augures* Varro says (L. L. 7. 7) *eius (caelestis templi) partes quattuor dicuntur, sinistra ab oriente, dextra ab occasu, antica ad meridiem, postica ad septentrionem. In terris dictum templum locus augurii aut auspicii causa quibusdam conceptis verbis finitus. The limits of the terrestrial templum were marked out by posts or otherwise: Paul. p. 157 M 'templum' est locus ita effatus aut ita saeptus ut ex una parte pateat, angulosque habeat adfixos ad terram; Serv. A. 4. 200 ... palis aut hastis aut aliqua tali re, et lineis aut loris aut simili re saeptum est. For the mode in which the *augures* marked out the celestial and terrestrial templa comp. further Liv. 1. 18, Fest. p. 220, Serv. A. 1. 92, 6. 191, Isid. Or. 15. 4. 7. A terrestrial templum might either be *sacrum* or not. All *senatus consulta*, in order to be legal, had to be passed in a templum, which however might be not *sacrum* but *profanum*; Varro ap. Gell. 14. 7. 7 *docuit confirmavitque nisi in loco per augures constituto, quod templum appellaretur, senatus consultum factum esset, iustum id non fuisse. Propterea et in curia Hostilia et in Pompeia et post in Iulia, cum profana ea loca fuissent, templa esse per augures constituta, ut in iis senatus consulta more maiorum iusta fieri possent. Inter quae id quoque scriptum reliquit, non omnes aedes sacras templa esse, ac ne aedem quidem Vestae templum esse: so also Varro L. L. 7. 10; Serv. A. 7. 153, ib. I. 446 erant ... templa in quibus auspiciato et publica res administratur et senatus haberi possit, erant tantum sacra: comp. Serv. A. 4. 200 (Nettleship, 1889).**

According to Nettleship, 1889, "The usages of the word are as follows.

1. A region in general, space; so with gen. of definition, an abode: ...

2. A place consecrated by the augurs, whether for public business or public worship: Cic. Vatin. 24 in rostris, in illo, inquam, augurato templo et loco; Legg. 2. 21 templa liberata et effata habento; Varro L. L. 6. 53 effari dicuntur templa ab auguribus; Verg. A. 7. 174 hoc illis curia templum, etc. (comp. A. 1. 504); Liv. 8. 13. 12 rostraque id templum appellatum; 23. 10. 5 egressus curia in templo magistratum consedit; Vitruv. 8. pr. 4 ad templum aedemque; Ov. M. 15. 800 strictique feruntur In templum gladii, neque enim locus ullus in urbe Ad facinus diramque placet nisi curia caedem; Vitruv. 4. 1. 5 deorum immortalium templa constituentes coeperunt fana aedificare.

3. In literature, as by Cic., Verg., Hor., Vitruv., etc., templum is often used loosely as synonymous with fanum and aedes sacra in the sense of temple, sacred building. Varro L. L. 7. 10 observes that aedes sacra and templum were often confused in current language and ideas.

4. Templum sometimes (from its meaning a line of division) stands for a crossbeam: Fest. p. 367 tignum quod in aedificio transversum ponitur; so Vitruv. 4. 2. I supra cantherios templa, deinde insuper sub tegulas asseres; so ib. 5, 4. 7. 5. [Vaniček connects templum with ten-=stretch : Fick with tap- (tep-or, tep-idus, etc.), warm. But the most natural course is with Nissen [Heinrich] to derive it from tem-, to divide. The idea of division suits all the usages, and notably (4). Templum then may stand for tem-lum, and be related to tem- as exemplum to exim-. On the whole subject see Nissen's work, Das Templum, and Marquardt, Röm. Staatsverwaltung 3. p. 385." (Nettlehip, 1889).

The Templum (Nissen, 1869, Catalano, 1978)

Heinrich Nissen was a German scholar of philology and ancient history. Among his books we find the *Italischen Landeskunde* (1883, 1902) and the *Das Templum* (1869). Being his work organized to show the role of orientation in the layout of temples, Nissen is credited being among the first 'archaeoastronomers' in the world (Ruggles, 2005). In his *Das Templum* of 1869, Nissen considered specifically the inaugurated place, which is defined as "templum". As previously told, the templum was a special place where the Roman augurs asked for Iuppiter's approval. It was, therefore, a specific place, on the ground and in air, managed by augurs, priests and officials of Rome. The augur practiced augury, the interpretation of the will of Iuppiter by studying events he observed within the predetermined sacred space, and the templum corresponded to the heavenly space above it.

Here it is necessary to read Catalano, 1978. "Colui che consulta Iuppiter attraverso l'arte augurale (in particolare i signa ex cáelo ed ex avibus) designa, in riferimento ad un luogo in terris, un luogo in aere entro cui, in base alla legum dictio, i signa assumono definiti significati in risposta alla domanda (si est fas). Questo modo di consultare la divinità attraverso la designazione di un templum aereo è comune non solo ai Latini, ma anche agli Osco-Umbri: ... Il *Valeton* aveva notato che non solo la legum dictio, ma anche il templum aereo sono elementi caratteristici della divinazione italica, mentre sembrano mancare a Greci e ad Etruschi. Non si può certo dire che questi due elementi non trovino corrispondenti presso altri popoli; certo è però che essi rivelano come, in ambiente italico, la divinazione augurale abbia avuto un particolare sviluppo in riferimento ai signa imperativa (cioè, richiesti alla divinità su questioni prefissate e con modalità, appunto, definite)" (Catalano, 1978). The person who consults with Iuppiter through the art of augury (in particular, the signa ex cáelo and ex avibus) designates, with reference to a place in terris, a place in aere within which, on the basis of the legum dictio, the signa take on definite meanings in response to the question (si est fas). This way of consulting the divinity through the designation of an aerial templum is common not only to the Latins, but also to the Osco-Umbrians: ... Valeton had noted that not only the legum dictio, but also the aerial templum are characteristic elements of Italic divination, while they seem to be lacking in the Greek and Etruscan divinations. It certainly cannot be said that these two elements do not find correspondence among other populations; it is certain, however, that they reveal how, in the Italic environment, augural divination had a particular development in reference to the imperative signa (i.e. requested from the divinity on pre-established questions and in a precisely defined manner) (Catalano, 1978).

According to Nissen, 1869, the town was a templum. He proposed that the Dies Natalis (birthday) of the roman towns was coincident with the day, at the sunrise of which, the direction of the decumanus (the main street) was determined according to the sunrise azimuth. He further claimed that the day was coincident with a roman festival, proposing the example, besides that of Rome, of Brindisi. We know the Dies Natalis of Brindisi from Cicero's works. About his return in Italy after exile, Cicero says that he arrived in Brindisi, the birthday of his daughter Tullia. This day was also the Dies Natalis of Brundisium and of the Temple of Concordia in Capitol. Note that these days are three different days, that is they are three commemorations of three different events. But Nissen mystified the events turning them into an unintelligible mixture. In any case, Nissen assumes the birthday of colonies determined by sunrise and roman festival. The birthday of the roman colonies had been already studied by Mommsen, and [Mommsen had a very different position](#) (see Eckstein, 1979). For what is regarding the town as a templum, Valetton strongly criticized this fact. The town was not a templum, and we find the Valetton's opinion reiterated by Catalano, 1978. Valetton was not alone in criticizing Nissen's theory. We find also [Giulio De Petra, who in his recension](#) of the Das Templum noted that Nissen was using only literature evidence supporting his thesis. All the passages which were against his theory were not considered. Martin Erdmann too criticized the "solar" templum by Nissen. In particular, he stressed that it is not possible to pass the idea of an oriented "templum", from the Greek temples to the Roman towns. And this is perfectly in agreement with the Nettleship's discussion. Please be careful of the following fact. When you find mentioned together Nissen, Valetton, Erdmann, consider that Valetton and Erdmann strongly criticized the Nissen's solar theory. On the other hand, [Friederic Nietzsche](#) was using the Nissen's idea for his lesson on the Greek cult. When you find told that decumanus was oriented with the sunrise on specific dates of calendar, that is festivals, and you find mentioned Nissen and Valetton together, consider that Valetton strongly criticized the Nissen's theory of a town as a templum. Therefore, there was no reason, for Valetton, to link decumanus and sunrise. Actually Valetton does not mention sun or sunrise in his works.

Let me stress that, until my work (published on November 1, 2020) about the direction of the decumani (main streets) of the roman towns, the work by Nissen was completely ignored, in particular by people who studied the same subject, that is the Roman archaeoastronomy. For instance, Giulio Magli, the [only archaeoastronomer](#) in Italy, does not mention Nissen in his 2007 article. This article started a series of news about the birthdays of Italian towns, the last is that of Jesi. In Magli's work we find the roman town with the decumanus oriented to the sunrise the day of a roman festival. No mention to Nissen's work is given.

A bronze reproduction of the Piacenza Liver. Image courtesy Shonagon, Own work, CC0, https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fegato_di_Piacenza#/media/File:Foie_de_Plaisance.jpg

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Fegato di Falerii: “Fegato in terracotta da Falerii Veteres, tempio dello Scasato, 310-300 a.C. circa, Museo nazionale etrusco di Villa Giulia, Roma”, fine IV secolo a.C. (310-300 a.C.). Terracotta ritrovata in località "Lo Scasato", Civita Castellana, provincia di Viterbo. “Si ritiene risalga alla fine del IV secolo a.C. (310-300 a.C.), ma da alcuni studiosi il modello è datato intorno al II secolo a.C., da altri è considerato contemporaneo al modello di fegato di Piacenza. ... Lo studioso Walter Burkert, uno dei massimi esperti della fase orientalizzante, ritiene che la diffusione dell'epatoscopia in Grecia e in Italia sia uno degli esempi più chiari di contatto culturale nel periodo orientalizzante tra mondo occidentale e mondo orientale, e che sia dovuta a piccoli movimenti migratori di personaggi carismatici provenienti dal mondo orientale, di cui non possiamo aspettarci di trovare molte tracce archeologicamente identificabili”. Terracotta liver from Falerii Veteres, temple of Scasato, c. 310-300 BC, National Etruscan Museum of Villa Giulia, Rome, end of the fourth century BC (310-300 BC). Terracotta found in the locality of "Lo Scasato", Civita Castellana, province of Viterbo. It is believed to date back to the end of the fourth century BC (310-300 BC), but by some scholars the model is dated around the second century BC; other scholars consider it contemporary with the liver model of Piacenza. ... The scholar Walter Burkert, one of the leading experts on the Orientalizing phase of Etruscan culture, believes that the spread of hepatoscopy in Greece and Italy is one of the clearest examples of cultural contact during the Orientalizing period between the Western and Eastern worlds, and that it is due to small migratory movements of charismatic persons from the Eastern world. Of this migration, we cannot expect to find many archaeologically identifiable traces.

Date and provenance

Let us return to the liver. The book by Van der Meer, 1987, entitled “The bronze liver of Piacenza” is regarding the “Iecur Placentinum”, the bronze model of a sheep's liver found in 1877. It is bearing 42 Etruscan inscriptions. “Once it was used by an Etruscan haruspex, probably about 100 B.C. The model is a real hapax. No other liver model with inscriptions has been found in Italy. As elsewhere in the Mediterranean world, in the Mesopotamian regions and in the Greek world, the Etruscans used to consult the entrails, in particular the liver, of an animal in order to discover the intentions of the gods and to explore the near or sometimes distant future” (Van der Meer, 1987). The Piacenza Liver is consequently

a highly relevant document for the understanding of Etruscan religion and art of haruspices. Van der Meer defines it as a “network with the inscribed names of divinities”, depicting “a microcosmos reflecting the macrocosmos, the Etruscan division of heaven”. The object was largely studied by “the division of the liver into a *pars familiaris* and *pars hostilis*, as we know from written sources, is one of the most difficult questions. These problems have been discussed by Deecke (1880), Körte (1905), Thulin (1906), Pallottino (1956) and recently by Maggiani (1982). In the older studies many misreading of the inscriptions contributed to partial or unsatisfactory results” (Van der Meer, 1987).

“The date of the Bronze Liver is based on palaeographical grounds. Heurgon has devoted a study to the typical form of the letter *m*, which is unjustly called the Umbrian *m*. It appears to occur only in the area between Cortona, Chiusi and Siena, and at Gubbio. In the latter Umbrian city, it did not appear before about 120 B.C. in the *Tabula Iguvina V*. The Umbrians certainly borrowed letters from the Etruscan alphabet from the fourth century B.C. The oldest inscriptions with the typical *m* date from about 150 B.C. and the most recent, perhaps, from the end of the first century B.C. A point of reference is offered by the famous bronze boy with a duck from Montecchio near Cortona with an inscription dedicated to *Thuflltha*. Because of its style this statuette is generally dated about 150 B.C. Heurgon suggests that the liver was made at Cortona, because this city was a production centre of bronzes and because the names of gods which occur on the Liver (*Tin, Uni, Thuflltha, Selvans*) are also to be found on several objects from the city and its vicinity” (Van der Meer, 1987).

“Apart from the typical *m*, Maggiani has paid attention to the *u/v* shift and to the fact that only one type of sibilant is used (the *s*, and not the *ç*). Because of similarities with the inscription from the *Tumulus of the Marconi* at Asciano he concludes that the liver has to be dated about 100 B.C. It would have been made to the north-west of Chiusi, in the area between Montepulciano and Asciano. Colonna notes that the Liver shows the letters of the North Etruscan alphabet, with the exception of the final *s*. Instead of the North Etruscan *ç* a South Etruscan *s* is used. This letter is rare in the area around the Trasimeno Lake but frequent outside Etruria, in Umbria, on the Adriatic coast zone between Pesaro and Rimini and in the Romagna. The famous bilingual inscription of Pesaro, dated c. 50 B.C., offers the best parallel, not only for the final *s* but for the typical *l* and *t* too. Colonna therefore assumes that the Liver was made outside Etruria, at Piacenza, and suggests that the Liver's having been found in the neighborhood of that city substantiates his argument. Moreover, Roman authors mention the presence of Etruscans in the Po valley even after the foundation of Roman colonies (Piacenza in 218 B.C., and Cremona in 188 B.C.)” (Van der Meer, 1987).

“Colonna's hypothesis is suggestive but one can argue that until now few Etruscan archaeological (and no epigraphical!) remains have been found at Piacenza. The few finds date from before the Celtic invasion. The period after the foundation of Roman *Placentia* has not yielded any Etruscan object with or without inscription. The exact place where the Liver was made cannot be established. Most probably it was made in the territory to the north-west of the Trasimeno Lake. In that region votive inscriptions mention some rare gods of the Liver (e.g. *Tec(vm)*) which do not occur elsewhere in Etruria. The *terminus post quem* is c. 150 B.C., the *terminus ante quem* c. 30/20 B.C., the period of the latest Etruscan inscriptions. A date about 100 B.C. seems most probable. How the object arrived in a field at Gossolengo is unknown. Perhaps an Etruscan haruspex serving a Roman general lost it during a military campaign. The following events, between c. 150 and 30 B.C., may be considered: a) the defeat of *Cn. Papirius Carbo* by Sulla's general, *M. Aemilius Lucullus* in 82 B.C. b) the expedition of Pompey against *M. Aemilius Lepidus* in 77 B.C., or c) the mutiny of Caesar's legions at Piacenza in 49 B.C. But we cannot exclude the possibility that the Liver was lost at a much later period, even in the first century A.D., since it could be bequeathed by father to son” (Van der Meer, 1987).

In the Appendix, some passages from the review by Linderski of “The bronze liver of Piacenza. Analysis of a polytheistic structure” are considered.

Morandi, 1988

“Il fegato bronzeo di Piacenza con le sue numerose e fitte iscrizioni ha posto sempre dei seri problemi per una esatta lettura. Nella storia degli studi si può osservare però che è mancato un impegno epigrafico vero e proprio da parte degli etruscologi, attratti da suggestioni spesso estranee alla natura intrinseca del testo. I recenti lavori del Maggiani e del Van der Meer hanno ora avviato proficue riletture del monumento iscritto, riletture che l'autore del saggio che qui si presenta cerca di perfezionare aggiungendo alcune considerazioni esegetiche a carico soprattutto della sequenza metlvmθ. Nel complesso viene offerta una riedizione ecdotica, unitamente ad un nuovo apografo il più possibile aderente alla realtà epigrafica. Con un buon margine di credibilità, l'autore ritiene di aver individuato in un gruppo di lettere il nome di Turan, dea finora considerata assente sul fegato; a questa divinità viene associato il nome di Laran, tracciato sulla vesica fellea, nella trasposizione etrusca corrispettivo di Ares, amante di Afrodite (Turan in etrusco)” (Morandi 1988). The bronze liver of Piacenza, with its numerous and dense inscriptions, has always posed serious problems for its exact reading. In the history of related studies, however, it can be observed that there has been a lack of a real epigraphic commitment on the part of Etruscologists, attracted by suggestions often extraneous to the intrinsic nature of the text. The recent works by Maggiani and Van der Meer have now initiated fruitful rereading of the inscribed monument, rereading that the author of the essay presented here [Morandi] seeks to perfect by adding some exegetical considerations especially regarding the sequence metlvmθ. Overall, an exegetical re-edition is offered, together with a new apograph as close as possible to the epigraphic reality. With a good margin of reliability, the author believes he has identified in a group of letters the name of Turan, a goddess until now considered absent on the liver; this deity is associated with the name of Laran, traced on the vesica fellea, in the Etruscan transposition equivalent of Ares, lover of Aphrodite (Turan in Etruscan).

Deecke and the three Templa

Van der Meer tells that “the anonymous farmer who found the Liver, don Fulcini, don Gazzolo, conte Caracciolo, director Mariotti and capitano Poggi did not recognize the object as a liver model. The same holds good for Deecke (1880) who, following Poggi, considered it a representation of a templum, a space divided by cardo and decumanus”: “Ich erkannte alsbald in dem Geräth das Bild eines etruskischen Templum, geleitet durch die übereinstimmung der Sechzehnteilung des Randes mit der Sechzehnteilung des Himmels.” [Deecke: I immediately recognized in the device the image of an Etruscan templum, guided by the correspondence of the sixteen-part division of the rim with the sixteen-part division of the sky].

Van der Meer notes that Deecke identified gods in the marginal regions of the liver/templum with gods given by Martianus Capella in his *De nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii*. “In his opinion the line between the left and right lobes was the decumanus and the non-continuous line starting between regions 16 and 1 and between 10 and 11, along the length of the Liver, was the cardo. Only in 1905 did Körte see in the bronze the model of a sheep's liver. Like Deecke he held the line between left and right lobe to be the east-west line. The right lobe would be the *pars familiaris*, and the left one the *pars hostilis*. ... The most detailed study, by Thulin, appeared in 1906. This famous scholar saw in the marginal division a representation of the Etruscan celestial division. The inner regions would refer to liver consultation, the marginal ones to the consultation of lightning. The combination of two divination systems was explained by the fact that *haruspices* practised both disciplines” (Van der Meer, 1987).

Van der Meer tells that Deecke considered the liver a templum, without recognizing it being a model of sheep's liver, and that only in 1905 Körte saw in the bronze the model of a sheep's liver. The history is a little bit more complex, as we will see when mentioning Körte, 1905.

Let us start with the work by Deecke, precisely with that of 1883, in the Göttingen scholarly advertisements. *Das Templum* is the “der für die Auspicien abgegrenzte Raum. Der Verfasser unterscheidet, noch wei ter gehend als Regell, die verschiedenen Templa folgender maaßen ...”. Deecke, 1883, is making a review of a book by J. E. Kuntze, *Prolegomena zur Geschichte Rom's: Oraculum*.

Auspicium. Templum. Regnum. In the review by Deecke we find three templa: 1) das Himmelstemplum, 2) das Lufttemplum, and 3) das Erdtemplum. Deecke tells that the author, J. E. Kuntze, distinguishes the various temples as follows: 1) the templum of sky, hemispherical, oriented towards the south, for observing lightning; 2) the templum of air, cube-shaped, oriented according to the prevailing local conditions, later mainly towards the east, the area of flying birds, for observing their flight and their voices; 3) the earth templum, square in shape, originally oriented towards the west, later also towards the east, the area of walking and crawling animals, especially for observing the feeding of chickens (tripudium, auspicia pullaria). About the temple of air, Deecke observes the difficulties the augur had in marking a cube-shaped piece of air, recording its boundaries and classifying the phenomena within it. To Deecke seemed practically unthinkable. Likewise, the different orientation and the fundamental difference between the heavenly and earthly temples do not make sense to [Deecke]: the latter must rather have been an image of the former. The relevant studies on the bronze from Piacenza (W. Deecke *Etrusk. Forsch.* IV *das Templum von Piacenza*; V, 2 *die Leber ein Templum*; Stuttg., Heitz, 1880 and 1882) remained unknown to the author or were ignored by him. In any case, they would have broadened his field of view and deepened and concentrated his understanding, while the discipline falls apart in many ways. But at least the author follows the pattern of the Templum in the Roman house and its development, in which he essentially follows Nissen (that is, Heinrich Niessen, *Das Templum*, 1869); in the Roman camp, where he particularly emphasizes the importance of the propugnaculum with the aqua viva; in the layout of the city of Rome, and in Latium. Against Nissen and Regell he lets the oldest Rome be oriented to the west, as a double camp against the Etruscans, the pointed front washed by the Tiber. The via sacra is then the cardo; the decumanus, which crosses it at an oblique angle, runs from the porta Carmentalis between the Capitol and the Palatine to the middle of the Esquiline, between the Carinae and the Viminal. The author also draws parallels with the oldest house here: ... (see more in the review by Deecke, 1883)

In Kerns, 2022, about the work by Deecke we find told the following: “In an analysis of the Piacenza Liver, Pallottino investigated the relationship between the inscribed names of deities and the respective templum of each deity, referring to the celestial region they inhabited. Pallottino argued against the generally accepted interpretation by Deecke, proposing his own position for holding the liver, upon which he based his schema of celestial regions and their proprietor deities. His interpretation was that the subsequent scholars have used it in their connection of temple orientation to cosmology. Pallottino himself was primarily concerned with the interpretation of the liver, but noted in a later monograph that the deviation of Etruscan temples from the orientation of Greek temples to be noteworthy and based on religion” (Kerns, 2022). Kerns is referring to Deecke’s 1882, *Nachtrag zum templum von Piacenza (die Leber ein templum)*.

G. Körte, 1905

Before reading Deecke’s templum. Let us consider G. Körte, 1905.

Poggi, who had the original object available for this purpose, published it in three unpretentious but generally accurate outline drawings and the inscriptions were read carefully and in most cases correctly, and their meaning as names of gods was recognized. Deecke himself had attempted to explain the strange form in a work distinguished by its erudition and ingenuity and, based on the sixteen-part division of the edge and the inscriptions on the back, claimed the bronze as a templum, a device for observing celestial signs, at the same time believing that the size ratio of the two halves could be used to prove a connection to the orbits of the sun and moon. His illustrations are made from a plaster cast and reproduce the outline of the device more accurately than Poggi's, but the system of lines is not entirely accurate, but more regular than it actually is. The inscriptions are interpreted on the basis of the list of gods in Martianus Capella and, as is self-evident, with complete mastery of all the relevant material, but the readings have to be corrected several times because they are based only on a not particularly good cast. In some cases, Poggi had read more correctly (Körte, 1905).

Under the fresh impression of this work that was discussed publicly, [Körte] noticed in the museum of Volterra in the autumn of 1881 the lid figure of an alabaster ash box No. 136, which, as the only one of all that Körte knows of, holds an object in its left hand that is exactly the same as the Piacentine bronze. [Körte] immediately shared a drawing of it with Deecke and by the way mentioned that it was thought to be a liver in Volterra. Deecke seized on this hint - the examination of calf and sheep livers showed that it was undoubtedly correct and Deecke hastened to publish the interesting discovery as an addendum to his first paper. The question is: to what extent the results of Deecke's first paper on our bronze, in particular its designation as a templum, are still valid now that it has been recognized as a liver? (Körte, 1905).

Deecke himself essentially maintains this. So, he says, the meaning of the mathematical and arithmetic relationships he has demonstrated remains, as does the whole interpretation as a templum, only that the instrument represents a liver first and secondly a templum, so that we [Deecke] do indeed learn the plan of the templum from it, but not in its original purity, but rather transferred to the liver, which is not conceivable without certain variations and deviations (for example, the non-rectangular intersection of cardo and decumanus). After this, the astronomical significance of the instrument recedes; it hardly served for orientation; even the division of the sky for the observation of lightning and the flight of birds was hardly carried out with its help. But the gain for this liver is nevertheless extraordinary. All at once, according to Deecke, coherence is brought into the entirety of the Etruscan discipline: like the sky, the earth, every sacred area, a town, a camp, a place of worship, even the human being, the liver was also considered a templum and the haruspicin was based on the same foundation and pattern as augurium and fulguration. In [Körte's] opinion, these statements are essentially incorrect, or should be formulated differently, the bronze simply represents an animal liver, namely that of a sheep, the designation templum is inaccurate and misleading. By sticking to this designation, Deecke has closed himself off from a full understanding of the tradition of the practice of the haruspicin itself (Körte, 1905).

The fact that “the sky, the earth, every sacred area, a town, a camp, a place of worship, even the human being” are templa is what we find the *Das Templum*, 1969, Nissen.

The liver from Deecke, 1880.

The Nissen's Templum in Deecke's liver

Let us consider Deecke, 1880. Das Templum von Piacenza. Here some passages translated.

Pag.1 - The interesting object that I have decided to make the subject of this treatise was, according to the report of the discovery by A. G(aetano) Tononi, member of the Royal Deputation for the Patriotic History of Emilia, in Piacenza, dug up by a farmer while ploughing in a field belonging to the Counts Arcelli near Settima, municipality of Gossolengo, not far from Piacenza, which was also distinguished by the discovery of antiquities. He threw it under a tree and continued his work. In the evening, he fetched the tool, cleaned it of dirt and took it home. His padrone,...

Pag.2 - ... It is still in his possession. He had it drawn, photographed and cast in plaster. The chemist Dr. Dioscoride Vitali in Parma examined its composition and explained: "It consists mainly of copper with a relatively small admixture of tin, exactly the alloy that was so well known to the ancients and is usually called bronze." Traces of iron can also be found in it. The patina (rust) is genuine and as a bronze object that has been buried in the ground for a long time and exposed to atmospheric agents usually shows. A photograph was shown by Tononi in the spring of 1878 to his friend G. Mariotti, the director of the Royal Museum in Parma. He advised him to inform Captain Vittorio Poggi about it, a scientifically trained officer who had made a name for himself by publishing a series of Etruscan inscriptions that he had found in various places and who had shown himself to be experienced in such antiquities.

Pag.3 - He also declared himself willing to publish a report on the device, which he recognized as Etruscan, and Count Caracciolo let him take the original to Parma for a few days for more detailed study. Then, in the summer of 1878, Poggi's article "Di un bronzo Piacentino con leggende Etrusche" appeared in the *Atti e Memorie delle Deputazioni di Storia Patria dell'Emilia. Nuova Serie Vol. IV. Modena, Vincenzi, 1878*. In it, Poggi gives a short report and description of the find, correctly interprets the writing and then goes through the engraved names of the gods in 47 numbers, mostly reading correctly and, as far as a general knowledge of Etruscan could lead him, not interpreting them clumsily. The conclusion is a brief discussion of the possible meaning of the instrument, which he explains as a kind of amulet and ascribes to the "braided learning" of the Etruscans, not without expressing some general reservations about its authenticity. *Poggi, with whom I had previously corresponded, sent me a copy of his work. I immediately recognized the device as an image of an Etruscan templum, guided by the correspondence between the sixteenth division of the edge and the sixteenth division of the sky by the Etruscans. From the inscriptions on the back, I was easily able to explain the origin of the peculiar form, to fix the cardinal points, to unravel the meaning of the elevations on the surface and to decipher several gods' names more correctly or in a new way. At the same time, I discovered peculiar numerical relationships related to the irregular shape, which were certainly not accidental. I immediately shared my observations with several fellow researchers and friends, of whom Isaac Taylor published a very positive report in the Athenaeum (November 23, 1878, No. 2665).*

Pag.4 - *On the subject I discussed in particular with Heinrich Nissen, the great expert on the templum, who responded enthusiastically to my suspicions, opened up a few new points to me and became more and more inclined to believe in its authenticity. The professor of astronomy at the local university, Dr. Aug. Winnecke, also showed great interest in the remarkable device. In the meantime, I wrote to Poggi, asking him to clarify some points about which I had remained in doubt in his writing and illustration, and asking whether it might not be possible to obtain a physical replica of the original. ... Ariodante Fabretti wrote to me on 12 April 1879: "Il monumento piacentino, di cui ebbi un facsimile in gesso, mi ispirò così poca fiducia, che fui distolto dal prenderlo in serio esame; nè sono ancora disposto a crederlo genuino con tutto quel codazzo di divinità etrusche graficamente alterate".*

Pag.5 - I, on the other hand, see myself compelled to hold on to the authenticity of the monument for internal reasons, and now, after waiting for further opinions for a longer period, I want to submit the matter to the learned public for a decision. Before I now move on to the description, I would like to note about

the images on the plates that all four of them show the device in natural size, according to the most precise measurements ...

Pag.6 - ... The lines and letters on the top are deeply carved, ... The whole thing, if you turn N towards the body, fits very comfortably in the flat outstretched palm and even fills a moderately large hand. *Otherwise, it looks like an object designed to float on a liquid, so that one immediately thinks of the earth floating on water, a hypothesis that we will examine in more detail below. The surface is irregularly elliptical and has been described as kidney-shaped or shoe-sole-shaped.*

Deecke proposed a series of geometrical reconstruction by means of line and circles.

Pag.7 - ... What gives our construction convincing power is the surprising fact that the points N, A, B and S lie on one line, the longitudinal axis of the elliptical structure. The answer to the question of what the two circles obtained in this way mean is given by the back with its two inscriptions emanating from O: *usils* = "solis", (circle) of the sun, and *tivs* = "lunae", (circle) of the moon (see III).

Pag.8 - Of these words, *usil* in the nominative as the name of the sun god was already known from two Etruscan mirrors (Fabr. Corp. Insc. Ital. n. 2097 and 2142), but the genitive is formed like the common *avils* = "aetatis" (Deecke in Bezz. Ztschr. I, 271); the word *tivs*, however, provides the first striking proof of the authenticity of the device. ...

Pag.9 - ... If we now look at the top again, the larger half, facing north, is the sun's circle, the smaller half facing south is the moon's circle. But the drawing of the six-spoked wheel also fits the moon's circle perfectly. In the second volume of my Etruscan Research, on "Etruscan Coinage", I explained the wheel, which is so common on Etruscan coins and usually has six spokes, by saying that "the wheel, which rolls quickly in a circle around its own axis, was an apt symbol of the star rolling across the sky." But it was particularly popular as a symbol of the moon, which appears to move the fastest, and is therefore also found in combination with other lunar symbols, such as the running Gorgon, crescent moons, etc. On the other hand, the cone lying in the circle of the sun is reminiscent of the similarly shaped club, which is a

symbol of the sun god and is often found on Etruscan coins, usually next to the head of Hercules or Janus (Deecke, *Etr. Forsch.* II, p. 90-91, 110-11 and 128). But it is also important to take a closer look at the numerical relationships in order to discover, if possible, a hidden regularity in the apparent irregularity. First of all, the radius of the sun's circle, is related to that of the moon's circle, almost exactly as the apparent mean radius of the sun, is related to the apparent smallest radius of the moon, so that the different sizes of the two circles seem to reflect the relationship between the apparent sizes of the two celestial bodies, as well as could be measured at that time.

Pag.10 - Furthermore, the arc of the sun's circle following the edge through WNE is about $244 \frac{1}{2}^\circ$, the missing piece between W and E is about $115 \frac{1}{2}^\circ$. But the table in Nissen's *Templum* p. 244 shows that for Rome, i.e. central Italy, the daytime orbit of the sun on the winter solstice, December 22nd, the shortest day, is $115^\circ 46'$, and the nighttime orbit is therefore $244^\circ 14'$, a coincidence that cannot be accidental. Furthermore, since the moon rises about 4° higher on its orbit than the sun, its longest visible orbit for Rome or central Italy is about 252° , and the invisible piece is then 108° ; the measurement of the arc of the lunar circle W'SO' following the edge of the device, however, gives $251 \frac{1}{2}^\circ$, and the missing piece is $108 \frac{1}{2}^\circ$, i.e. a hardly less precise agreement. If we therefore consider, as we already suspected above, the entire device as an image of the earth floating on the sea, then the area marked by a hole just below the edge, from which, according to the inscriptions, the sun and moon emanate, must mean the east (see No. III). The opposite area is then west, the one on the right is north, the one on the left is south, and so I have designated them by the initial letters of the celestial regions. This is generally consistent with the greater concentration of the names of the gods towards the north and the pyramid located there, which presumably represents the mountain of the gods, since according to the Etruscan belief the gods lived in the north, or at least the highest, most powerful, most numerous had their home there (O. Müller II, p. 131; 133 etc.); I will prove this in particular below from the individual names of the gods.

Pag.11 - More precisely, in the solar circle, O is the rising point of the sun in the winter solstice, W the setting point; the missing arc not shown is therefore the above-ground or day part of the sun's orbit; WNO, on the other hand, indicates the larger underground or night part of the sun's orbit. If one calculates 90° on either side of N as the north point, one finds the characteristic circumferential points point S opposite N turns out to be the south point: otherwise, I am not familiar enough with the more complicated circumstances of the moon's orbit to venture any further individual interpretations. But with certainty NS turns out to be the line of noon, meridian, *cardo*, hinge line of the rotation of the celestial vault, the first line that the augur used to draw in the sky and correspondingly also on the earth (see O. Müller II, p. 130, and below). Then the line E W is to be considered as a crossing line, as a *decumanus*, for the whole of the sky, as well as the surface of the earth, and is also indicated on the underside as a broad, elevated road, like the *via decumana* in the Roman camp, the *limes decumanus* on the Roman field. This line also cuts through the quarter ellipsoid, in which one may perhaps recognize the earth's navel, if one supplements the irregularly elliptical surface of the earth with the surrounding sea to form a circle.

Pag.12 - It is striking, however, that the ellipsoid does not have its center point in C, but is shifted to W, and that the *decumanus* is not perpendicular to the *cardo*. Much remains unclear and left to be solved later. Since it is uncertain whether the Etruscans had the Egyptian-Babylonian division of the circle into 360° , I do not dare to assume that this deviation, which is about 10° , is connected with the name *decumanus*, which has not yet been clearly interpreted (see O. Müller II, p. 137, nt. 7). Now since we are directly referring to the Italian *templum*, by *cardo* and *decumanus*, it is important to test the further information about it on our instrument. First of all, I hold, against Nissen, to O. Müller's view (II2, p. 129), that the word *templum* by no means in itself contains the concept of the limited, as one has become accustomed to assume as a result of the etymological combination with *témenos*, *tempus*, etc.; even if the derivation of all these words from *Témnein*, *temnere* should be correct (Curt. Gr. Etym. 220; Corss. Krit. Beitr. 400), this still does not follow, since it can just as well be the "intersected" as the "circumcised" space. In any case, the entire visible sky is always divided by the augur with his staff. The same thing seems to be said in the main passage in Varro (*de lingua Lat.* VII, 7, p. 119 M.) with its different etymology: "*Quaqua intuitus (conjectur of O. Müller) erat oculi, a tuendo primum templum dictum.*"

Pag.13 - Quocirca caelum, qua attuimur, dictum templum." If this division of the heavens was transferred to the earth, as is established by many testimonies, e.g. Varro (ibid. VII, 6 *templum dicitur ab auspiciis in terra*), it is highly probable, indeed actually self-evident, that, although there is no definite statement about this, the entire surface of the earth was initially considered a *templum*, an image of the heavens, according to the view so widespread in antiquity that heavens were used as an example for earthly things. According to the general view of the microcosm in relation to the macrocosm, the limited spaces were also divided and named as *templum* for practical purposes: first perhaps a country, then the part of the earth's surface that can be seen from a higher point, e.g. the *arx* of a community (in Rome from the Capitol), then a city, a camp, a field, an area dedicated to some god or religious purpose, chosen for some religious act, whereby the division was then, naturally more or less, simplified. If we now remain with the division of the most original *templum*, the heavens, the Romans, and probably also the other Italians, divided them into 4 parts, the Etruscans into 16. When Cicero (*de divinat.* II, 18, 42) says of this: "*facile id quidem fuit, quattuor, quas nos habemus, duplicare: post idem iterum facere*", it is undoubtedly probable that the sixteen-part division was once preceded by a four-part, perhaps even an eight-part division, but it is premature to conclude that the special augural division of the heavens into four parts, as the Romans had it in Cicero's time, was the unaltered preservation of a primal, pre-Etruscan state.

Pag.14 - There is enough to suggest that the Romans too once knew the augural sixteenth division, probably borrowed from the Etruscans, and only later, because of the difficulty of handling, simplified it again as practical people even in religious matters. It was also hastily concluded from Cicero's passage that the 16 celestial regions of the Etruscans were of equal size. The idea is certainly plausible, but it is not exactly stated in Cicero's words, and even if Cicero meant it that way, which is what the "*facile*" could indicate, he may well have had insufficient knowledge of the Etruscans' "*abstruse and secret discipline*" on this point. The division of the sky into sixteen is mentioned in a similar way by Pliny the Elder (*N. H.* II, 54(55), 143) "*in sedecim partes caelum in eo spectu divisere Tusci*" and immediately afterwards "*has (the 4 main regions) iterum in quaternas divisere partes*"; by Servius (on the *Aeneide* VIII, 427) "*nam dicunt physici de sedecim partibus caeli iaci fulmina*"; and further "*fulmina Iupiter iacit toto caelo, hoc est de diversis partibus caeli, scilicet sedecim*". In all these places there is talk of lightning observation, which the Etruscans had developed very specifically in the *ars fulguritorum* (*O. Müll.* II, p. 166-180). The last and most important mention of the 16 regions, however, we find by a happy coincidence in the work of a tasteless but learned writer of the latest period, Martianus Capella, in his *Nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii*. Here (*lib. I, § 45-61; p. 16-17 G., p. 17-18 Eyss.*) a meeting of the gods is held to discuss a marriage project, and for this purpose the deities are invited from all 16 regions of heaven. It is told in § 45, "*in sedecim discerni dicitur caelum omne regiones*". Firstly, Capella observes that not all deities inhabit heaven or have a residence in it: "*ceteri di*", in § 61, "*azoni vocantur*", which expression, however, is perhaps based on a confusion of the sixteenth division with the twelfth division of the zodiacus;

Pag.15 - secondly, that Jupiter lives in all regions, and in fact in the highest, "*Domus Iovis in omnibus regionibus sublimis est*"; so he is also explicitly mentioned in the first three regions, in the fifth indirectly (in *coniuges reges*), in the sixth *Iovis filii*, etc. This is also consistent with the above passage by Servius, according to which Jupiter hurls lightning from all 16 regions of heaven, and was thus thought to live in all of them. Of the other gods residing in heaven it is said "*discretis plurimum locis deorum singuli mansitabant*", but some also had their residence in at least two or more regions, just as Jupiter lived in all of them, both in adjacent regions and in separate regions, as shown in drawing no. V. Martianus then gives a list of the deities living in each of the 16 regions, who are either invited or are already present with Jupiter, or are deliberately neglecting the invitation because they are hostile to marriage. Unfortunately, this list is rather incomplete, since as a rule, the gods already mentioned are not mentioned again in the other regions where they also lived, for example, in the eighth: "*octava vero transcurritur, quoniam ex eadem cuncti superius corrogati solusque ex illa "Veris fructus" adhibetur*." But even the hostile deities who were neglecting the invitation are not always mentioned, for example, "*ex duodecima Sancus tantummodo evocatur*." Furthermore, we do not know all the gods who were already present with Jupiter, nor from which region they came. Finally, the author who given the insignificance of the whole, was not concerned with completeness, seems to have used his source inadequately and arbitrarily.

Pag.16 - So the whole is only a fragment, albeit a highly valuable one. But that source, as the sixteenth division and as some details show at first glance, - I will prove in more detail below, - can be traced back to an Etruscan fulgural book; in a Roman version of a later period, the translation of the names into Latin and the admixture of many foreign, Roman, Italian, and Greek, doctrines of the gods, both cannot be attributed to Martianus. The passage by Martianus is treated in more detail in O. Müller's *Etruskern II*, pp. 128-136, where the notes I have added relating to the more recent research should also be noted, by H. Nissen in "Templum" p. 182 ff, also t. IV, and by Eyssenhardt in the introduction (pp. XXXIV-XLIII) to his edition of Martianus. Because of its tremendous importance, I am putting the whole passage here and ask you to compare it with No. V, where, following Nissen's procedure, from which I otherwise deviate on several occasions, the regions are made the same size: "Nec mora milites Iovis per diversas caeli regiones appropierant, quippe discretis plurimum locis deorum singuli mansitabant . . . Name in sedecim discerni dicitur caelum omne regiones. In quarum prima (I) sedes habere memorantur post ipsum Iovem di Consentes, Penates, Salus ac Lares, Janus, Favores, Opertanei Nocturnusque.

Pag.17-18-19 - In secunda (II) itidem mansitabant praeter domum Iovis, quae ibi quoque sublimis est, ut est in omnibus, Praediatus, Quirinus, Mars, Lar(s) militaris; Iuno etiam ibi domicilium possidebat, Fons etiam, Lymphae dique Novensiles .

Sed de tertia (III) regione unum placuit corrogari: nam Iovis Secundani et Iovis Opulentiae Minervaeque domus illic sunt constitutae, sed omnes circa ipsum Iovem fuerant in praesenti. Discordiam vero ac Seditionem quis ad sacras nuptias corrogaret praesertimque cum ipsi Philologiae fuerint semper inimicae? De eadem regione igitur solus Pluton, quod patruus sponsi est, convocatur. Tunc Lynsa silvestris, Mulciber, Lar caelestis, nec non etiam militaris 13), Favorque ex quarta (IV) regione venerunt.

Corrogantur ex proxima (V), transcursis domibus con iugum regum, Ceres, Tellurus, Terraeque pater, Vulcanus et Genius. Vos quoque, Iovis filii Pales et Favor cum Celeritate, Solis filia, ex sexta (VI) poscimini. Nam Mars, Quirinus et Genius superius postulati.

Sed etiam Liber ac Secundanus Pales vocantur ex septima (VII). Fraudem quippe ex eadem post longam deliberationem placuit adhiberi, quod crebro ipsi Cyllenio fuerit obsecuta.

Octava (VIII) vero transcurritur, quoniam ex eadem cuncti superius corrogati, solusque ex illa Veris fructus adhibetur. Iunonis vero Sospitae Genius accitus ex nona (IX).

Neptune autem et Lar omnium cunctalis ac Neverita tuque, Conse, ex decima (X) convenistis. Venit ex altera (XI) Fortuna et Valitudo, Pavore, Pallore 2) et Manibus refutatis, quippe hi in conspectum Iovis non poterant advenire. Ex duodecima (XII) Sancus tantummodo evocatur. Fata vero ex altera (XIII) postulatur: ceteri quippe illic di Manium demorati. Ex bis septena (XIV) Saturnus eiusque caelestis Iuno consequenter acciti. Veiovis ac di Publici ter quino ex limite (XV) convocantur.

Ex ultima regione Nocturnus Ianitoresque terrestres similiter advocati. Excunctisigitur caeli regionibus advocatis deis ceteri, quos Azonos vocant, ipso commonente Cyllenio convocantur.

The fact that the list begins from the north, from midnight, is shown by the Nocturnus in Regions XVI and I, and agrees with the above-mentioned view of the Etruscans that the main residence of the gods is in the north. It then goes through the east, which is certainly indicated by the Celeritas, Solis filia, in Region VI, and through the south, where the Lar omnium cunctalis in Region X is located, to the west, in which area of the sunset, according to general ancient opinion, mainly underworld gods live.

If we now compare our Placentine bronze with the heavenly temple of Martianus, the division of the edge into 16 regions is correct. A deviation then seems to lie in the fact that on the bronze the regions are of unequal length.

Pag.20 - But I have already pointed out above that there is nothing that forces us to assume that they were of the same size among the Etruscans: Martianus does not say this either. However, the other celestial points fall much more appropriately in the unequal division of the bronze than in Nissen's drawing: for only now does the Celeritas, Solis filia in Reg. VI (6) fall exactly on the east point, the Lar omnium cunctalis in Reg. X (10) really on the south point, and the Fata and ceteri di Manium in Reg. XIII (13) fall at least as well to the left as to the right of the west point. A second deviation seems to lie in the fact that on the bronze the peripheral regions are separated from the interior, which shows its own artificial divisions, while Nissen's drawing according to Martianus assumes that each peripheral region, in the shape of a section of a circle, reaches up to the zenith. But here too the latter assumption is a hypothesis founded on nothing, except that perhaps another arrangement would have been too complicated. But the disciplina Etruscorum was, according to Varro, ars "recondita et abstrusa" and the division and observation of the sky was an art that was difficult to learn and practiced as a profession by special experts. On closer inspection, however, it also emerges that in the lunar circle of the bronze, the 6 peripheral regions correspond to 6 wheel cutouts, and in fact wheel cutouts touch the peripheral regions 9 and 10 and show the same names of the gods, so that the distribution of the other 4 wheel cutouts to the other peripheral regions, as I have shown in the same numbers, leaves no doubt. But the same simple result also arises in the solar circle if one ignores the central region and the cone and only sticks to the drawing on and under the pyramid, i.e. to the part lying north from the line O' W" (see No. IV).

And the author continues with the description, and discussions about the names of deities and the letters used for the inscriptions.

Finally, if we summarize the results of this investigation, the instrument, in addition to symbolizing the religious and worldview of the ancient Etruscans in a mysterious way and representing certain astronomical relationships concerning the sun and moon, may also have served practically, both for orientation and determination of the regions of the sky, and as a model for dividing the horizon, the vault of heaven and the surface of the earth. As already noted above, it lies comfortably in the outstretched hand, with N towards the body, so that when the augur or fulguritor turned towards the south, as was the rule with the Etruscans and Italians when describing the Templum, the point S was actually facing south. I imagine that the augur held the instrument in his left hand, took the lituus in his right hand (*dextra manu tenens lituum* in Liv. I, 18), first drew the *cardo* by raising the staff backwards over his head and moving it forwards, then the *decumanus* from left to right, then according to the surface of the bronze in his left hand, as if from a map, divided the horizon and the vault of heaven or the surface of the earth (see the division of the *vinea* by Attus Navius in Cicero *de. divin.* I, 17, 31) in detail and finally, always regarding the bronze, observed the signs in the selected regions. The difficulty of such division and observation, given the irregularity and artificiality of the drawing, gives us for the first time a real idea that the *disciplina Etruscorum* was in fact *occulta* and *abstrusa*. How the genuine Etruscan regional division thus obtained relates to the orientation of the ancient Italian, especially Roman, temples, cities, camps, etc., requires a new investigation, which is very difficult given the poorness and uncertainty of the material in question and can only be carried out on site.

Very good observation made by Deecke indeed.

Further information

Patrick Hunt, "Reading livers through reading literature: Hepatoscopy and haruspicy in ILIAD 20:469 FF & 24:212 FF, AENEID 4:60 FF & 10.175 FF, CICERO and PLINY on Divination, among others. Sept 28, 2007, [web archive](#). "Divination by interpreting livers in the ancient world from Mesopotamia to the Mediterranean and from the Bronze Age to the Classical world is a fascinating topic for study of religion, magic and science. Complicated long-term traditions governed haruspicy or hepatoscopy, i.e., liver interpretation or examination. One primary question to be asked is why was a liver used for divination and why a sheep's liver, as this appears to be the most common organ used across many cultures and periods? Here are some tentative thoughts. 1) Although it is relative to how much wealth individuals might possess, sheep were more easily sacrificed as smaller animals than expensive cattle". ... etc.

Collins, 2008, writes about the "Mapping the entrails: The practice of Greek hepatoscopy". Collins' article "reconstructs the practice of Greek hepatoscopy in the classical period and thereafter. Based on historical, literary, and comparative anthropological material, it argues that hepatoscopy was a binary system involving both fixed and fluid points of reference on animal livers. Attention is given to the most relevant features of the liver as they pertain to divination, in both Greek and later Roman sources, as well as to the seers who specialized in this form of divination. Finally, [Collins] contrast[s] Greek liver divination with a contemporary African example of entrails-reading in an effort to illustrate how Greek hepatoscopy might have proceeded".

Orhun, 2009, considers the "fortune-telling of liver, bird-flying in Hittites and their tracks on Etruscans". "As in all ancient societies, Hittites and Etruscans also developed certain techniques of fortune-telling to know about the theological wish, among which were fortune-telling of liver or bird-flying. In [Orhun'] study, in spite of the highly distant time zones of Hittites and Etruscans, these two similar techniques were depicted. In that way, it is correlated that there could be a cultural link between Hittites, who established a prominent civilization in Anatolia, and Etruscans, assumed to be an Anatolian originated society before establishing another prominent civilization in Europe, who also had a prominent effect on Roman culture".

Bachvarova, 2012, too investigated the transmission of hepatoscopy from East to West. “The spread of hepatoscopy is one of the clearest examples of cultural contact in the orientaling period. It must have been a case of East-West understanding on a relatively high, technical level. The mobility of migrant charismatics is the natural prerequisite for this diffusion, the international role of sought-after specialists, who were, as far as their art was concerned, nevertheless bound to their father-teachers. We cannot expect to find many archaeologically identifiable traces of such people, other than some exceptional instances”.

“Walter Burkert's theory of freely moving craftsmen of verbal art and ritual technology bringing stories and magico-religious practices to the west in the orientaling period (750-650 BCE) has caught the imagination of Classical scholars and been given great explanatory power in subsequent discussions of textual and cultural links across the Mediterranean. By simply referring to the theory as a given, Classical scholars have been able to avoid the questions of why and how, and to move directly to a discussion of the motifs or practices under consideration, using the Near Eastern sources to analyze Greek cultural artifacts. ... Key to Burkert's argument concerning the role of itinerant diviners transmitting cultural features is the shared practice of liver divination. He argues, first, that parallels in the terminology of Greek and Akkadian hepatoscopy are evidence that the Greek hepatoscopic tradition was influenced directly by the Mesopotamian practice; secondly, he sees the bronze liver model found at Piacenza in Italy as directly related to the second-millennium Near Eastern liver models (he does not discuss the uninscribed terra cotta liver from Falerii Veteres); and finally, he argues that "migrant charismatics" brought the practice to the west” (Bachvarova, 2012).

Bachvarova discussed “the relationship between the Near Eastern liver models and the two Etruscan liver models. [Bachvarova] side[s] with those scholars who see a west Anatolian origin for the Etruscans, suggesting that the immigrants brought liver divination with them, and that the uninscribed Falerii liver is evidence for the way in which Etruscan haruspicy was practiced before the major transformation shown by the Piacenza liver, in which gods and areas of the heavens are associated with areas of the liver”.

Aveni and Romano, 1994

We have seen that in the Deecke's templum, the author discusses in detail the list given by Martianus Capella. Let us stress that Capella, as told by Deecke too, was considered by Nissen, and in fact, in the Das Templum, we can find an illustration with the sixteen subdivisions of the sky in Capella's deities.

An often-mentioned article by archaeoastronomers is that by Aveni and Romano, 1994, where we can find Nissen and his Das Templum among the given references. However, Aveni and Romani are referring just to the data provided by Nissen in his book about the orientation of temples. We find just reference to the data, and nothing more, of the large work made by Nissen regarding the templum. However, in Aveni and Romano we find proposals, the seeds of which we can clearly evidence in Das Templum.

Here in the following an example from Aveni and Romano. After a long description of the liver of Piacenza, we find a section entitled “How are the temples oriented? The archaeological data”. “There is yet another astronomical possibility [for the orientation of the temples]. The most easterly temples (and those close to west for that matter) could be oriented to the sunrise (sunset) not on the equinox, but on dates that correspond to certain sacred festivals, perhaps left over from an archaic solar cult. If the Etruscans themselves passed such information forward in time, and the Romans were receptive to it, we might expect fragments to show up in the Roman calendar. To explore this possibility, we have converted the axial orientations into dates of the seasonal year for all temple orientations that fall within the course of the sun along the horizon. There are two possible dates for each orientation. Then we examined a list of Roman feriae to see whether Roman deities to whom the festivals are dedicated might in any way resemble Etruscan deities known to have been associated with specific temples. The results are summarized in TABLE” by Aveni and Romano. These are Aveni and Romano words. No reference given. No reference to Nissen.

Note please that Nissen considers the direction of the long axis of the temple as oriented along the sunrise. He argues that, if we do not know the deity to which the temple was dedicated, we can compare the azimuth of the axis with the sunrise azimuth, finding the corresponding day, and compare with the calendar and festivals we find in it. Therefore, if we measure the azimuth of the temple's axis and determine the date, we can find with a comparison with the calendar's festival, the name of the deity to which the temple was dedicated. But the dedication of a temple is the last formal act of the long sequence of its building, not the first one. About the calendar, De Petra noted in his review of the *Das Templum*, that the idea is interesting. However, there is a problem because the Greek and Roman calendars were luni-solar, besides being often irregular. And the same we can tell for the proposal by Aveni and Romano. The problem is the same.

Here a screenshot from Nissen's *Das Templum*.

16. Jupiter, Pompeji 337°.

Ueber sein Verhältniß zum Forum vgl. S. 142, seine Stellung im Staat S. 145. Desgleichen ward S. 131 Liber als italischer Nationalgott und identisch mit Jupiter nachgewiesen; die *descriptio caeli*, welche in der 7. Region nur ersteren, nicht letzteren nennt, gewährt für jene Auseinandersetzung eine neue Bestätigung. — Was beim vorhergehenden Tempel über die Beziehung der Queraxe zum Sonnenaufgang gesagt wurde, trifft auf den des Jupiter auch deutlich zu. Der Untergang von 67° fällt auf 2 3. Februar 11/12. November. Der 13. Nov. *epulum Iovis* ist einer der Haupttage dieses Gottes. Dem 13. Nov. entspricht iulianisch Febr. 1, der weiter nicht im **Kalender** bezeichnet ist; allein alle Kalenden sind der Juno heilig. Der Aufgang mit 247° trifft iulianisch auf 9. Mai 9. August: man wird vielleicht zu setzen haben 7. Mai 13. August, letzteres ein Jupiterfest, erstere die Nonen, an denen gleichfalls stets Opfer dargebracht wurden; doch ist dies sehr unsicher. Die *descriptio caeli*

As previously told, Nissen linked decumani and sunrise. Nissen's direction of decumanus, coincident to a sunrise azimuth, and the link to Roman festivals, is given in Chapter VI of *Das Templum*. The "Nissenschen Theorie" is also reported by Friedrich Nietzsche in his lesson about *Der Gottesdienst der Griechen*. Here what Nissen is telling "Diese Erklärung, welche sich aus den Worten der Gromatici mit Notwendigkeit ergibt, eröffnet eine ganz neue Betrachtungsweise. Wie jeder Mensch, so hat auch der Gott und die Götterwohnung und das Templum in seinen verschiedenen Anwendungen überhaupt einen Geburtstag. Dies gilt ebenso von der Stadt: einige Geburtsjahre italischer Städte sind S. 56 zusammengestellt. So wenig wir hiervon wissen, erscheint unsere Kunde bezüglich der Geburtstage doch noch weit dürftiger. Für Rom wird er bezeichnet durch das Parilienfest am 21. April, für die Colonie Brundisium durch das Fest der Salus auf dem Quirinal am 5. August. Nach dem oben Gesagten muss also die Richtung des Decumanus entsprechen dem Sonnenaufgang am Gründungstag des Templum. Und um die Theorie auf gegebene Fälle anzuwenden, lässt sich aus dem Decumanus der Gründungstag finden, oder falls der Tag bekannt, die Richtung des Decumanus".

In the first part of the Chapter, Nissen is proposing selected well-known sentences from the Roman surveyors' literature in Latin (for supporters of the orientation to sunrise of decumani it is enough to copy and past them, and translate from German the related discussions). Heinrich Nissen claims that he has explained the meaning of the sentences. The text in German says that this explanation, which necessarily follows from the words of the gromatici, opens up an entirely new way of looking at these things. Like every human being, gods and god' temples - or the Templum in its various applications - have a birthday in general. This also applies to the town: some years of birth of Italian cities are given S. 56. Little we know about years then, and our sources seem even poorer when it comes to birthdays. For Rome it is designated by the festival of Parilie on April 21st, for the Colony Brundisium, by the festival of Salus on the Quirinal on August 5th. According to the discussion above, the direction of the decumanus must

correspond to the sunrise on the day the Templum was founded. And to apply the theory to given cases, the founding day can be found in the Decumanus, or if we know the day, the direction of the Decumanus is given.

Nissen's conclusions are coming from his interpretation of the literature of Roman surveyors and of Roman mythology. His approach had a consequence: the birthday of a colony was associated with the day when the direction of its decumanus was determined, but this is not true (see discussions by Eckstein and Conventi). As evidenced by Giulio De Petra in his review of *Das Templum*, Nissen was choosing only those passages useful for his ideas and avoided to consider other passages which were not in agreement with his theory.

In Aveni and Romano we find Martianus Capella and the liver discussed in detail. We can find also told that the liver was considered a templum (no reference is given), but it is told: "The liver itself was considered a templum, and we [Aveni and Romano] ought to reflect on just why it was viewed in this way. The Etruscans believed in a one-to-one correspondence between the macroscopic structure of the world and the microscopic organization of its component parts [no reference given]. Why choose the liver? Jastrow (1908) has traced the practice of hepatoscopy ... [Jastrow proposed a "Hepatoscopy and astrology in Babylonia and Assyria", <https://www.jstor.org/stable/983836>, Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society, Vol. 47, No. 190 (Sep. - Dec., 1908), pp. 646-676 (31 pages); among Aveni and Romano references we find a misprint; the work is given as JASTROW, M. 1908. Hepatoscopy & astrology in Babylonia & Greece, Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society 47(190): 646-96]. ... In the Piacenza liver we [Aveni and Romano] glimpse a point of contact between man and god in which the question of orientation was central. If the temple was a place for establishing communication between gods and people, and if the gods live in precisely partitioned houses, then the temple and its rites must be connected to the locations of the deities in space via orientation. Thus our [Aveni and Romano] goal in the next section will be to inquire into the practical matter of acquiring temple alignments, based upon the surviving archaeological record" (Aveni and Romano, 1994). Please, consider again the G. Körte, 1905, and his discussion of Deecke's work. About the templum, please consider again the words by Pierangelo Catalano, 1978.

Let us conclude this section stressing once that, until my work (Sparavigna, November 1, 2020) about the direction of the decumani (main streets) of the Roman towns, the work by Nissen was completely ignored by people who studied the same subject, that is the Roman archaeoastronomy, and the Etruscan archaeoastronomy too. Giulio Magli does not mention Nissen in his 2007 article, the article that started a series of news about the birthdays of Italian towns. Aveni and Romano does not properly consider the Nissen's theory exposed in his book. It seems that they have only considered the tables in Nissen's books and did not read it. We find in their work of 1994 the same proposal of comparison with festivals for the temples that was proposed in Nissen. Only data are considered. But data are a negligible thing, with respect to the ideas exposed in the Nissen's book. The idea that the town is a templum is wrong, and to understand the reasons we need the detailed studies made by Valeton, and more recently by Catalano. The idea that the Dies Natalis is linked to the direction of the temple is wrong, because its Dies Natalis is determined by the consecration/dedication to the deity as his/her dwelling place. Therefore, there is no reason to compare the day of the sunrise in the direction of the long axis of it to the festivals of the calendar.

From the review by Giulio De Petra of *Das Templum*

Here we propose how De Petra explains the Nissen theory in *Das Templum*.

"La ragione è, che la direzione verso oriente non esprime d'ordinario un dato fisso, non indica l'oriente equinoziale, ma l'oriente di un determinato giorno dell'anno, ben sapendo gli antichi, che il Sole muta di posto ogni giorno, e che il punto oriente di ieri non sarà quello di domani. Quel determinato giorno, a cui si riferisce l'orientazione del tempio, non può esser altro che il giorno della fondazione, cioè della consecrazione: apud Romanos nihil fuit tam solemne, quam dies consecrationis (SERV. ad Aen VIII .

600). [Il giorno della consacrazione del tempio non è il giorno in cui si stabilisce il suo asse lungo. La consacrazione/dedica è l'atto finale, non quello iniziale. Sparavigna] A quel modo che il fondatore della città osservava con la groma il punto dell'orizzonte, ove in quel giorno spuntava il Sole, e quindi sulla linea del raggio solare che veniva indicata dalla groma, tirava il decumano (posita auspicaliter groma, ipso forte conditore praesente, proximum vero ortum comprehenderunt, et in utramque partem limites emiserunt HYGIN., p. 170), al modo stesso facevasi nella fondazione del tempio. Perciò la direzione dell'asse di questo, cioè del decumano, era in corrispondenza col giorno della fondazione; e quindi conosciuta quella, si può conoscere con un calcolo astronomico anche questo. D'altra parte, le feste in onore di una divinità s'istituivano d'ordinario, per ricordare il giorno della fondazione di un tempio ad essa dedicato. [Si noti che la festa del tempio coincide con la consacrazione/dedica del tempio alla divinità e ne sancisce l'apertura al pubblico. Non è pertanto il giorno di fondazione, se per giorno di fondazione intendiamo l'inizio dei lavori, Sparavigna]. Festo ne porge due esempi specchiatissimi: Martias calendas matronae celebrabant, quod eo die Iunonis Lucinae aedis coli coepta erat (p. 147); Quinquatrus... Minervae autem dicatum eum diem existimant, quod eo die aedis eius in Aventino consecrata est (p. 257). Onde è, che avuto dall'orientazione del tempio il giorno della sua fondazione, se in quel giorno o nei vicini il calendario pone una festa, ci è tutta la probabilità che il dio in onore di cui facevasi quella festa, fosse anche il dio al quale era stato innalzato quel tempio. Questa è la nuova teoria dell'Autore [Nissen] sull'orientazione degli antichi templi. Il fondamento su cui riposa è ragionevolissimo, perché non [De Petra trova] che possa oppugnarsi il presupposto che stabilisce, avere gli antichi trovare fra i segni del cielo e i templi dei Numi in terra. Le speciali applicazioni, che il Nissen fa di questo principio alle antichità greche ed italiche, sono da lui dimostrate con buoni argomenti. Solo ci è, che l'utilità pratica della sua teoria rimane in un campo assai ristretto. Perché dati gli aiuti astronomici per trovare l'orientazione del tempio, supposta anche una profonda conoscenza dell'antica cronologia, per tradurre con la possibile esattezza i giorni ed i mesi nostri nei giorni e nei mesi dei calendari anteriori alla riforma giuliana, romane sempre come desideratum la completa conoscenza delle feste antichissime." (Giulio De Petra, 1869).

De Petra reports the Nissen's theory in the following manner.

The reason is that the direction towards the east does not usually express a fixed datum, it does not indicate the equinoctial east, but the east of a certain day of the year, the ancients knowing well that the Sun changes position every day, and that the east point of yesterday will not be that of tomorrow. That certain day, to which the orientation of the temple refers, can only be the day of the foundation, that is, of the consecration: apud Romanos nihil fuit tam solemne, quam dies consecrationis (SERV. ad Aen. VIII. 600) [Please consider that the consecration/dedication of the temple is the last act of the long sequence of actions related to the building of the temple, Sparavigna]. In the same way that the founder of the city observed with the groma the point of the horizon, where on that day the Sun rose, and therefore on the line of the solar ray that was indicated by the groma, he drew the decumanus (posita auspicaliter groma, ipso forte conditore praesente, proximum vero ortum comprehenderunt, et in utramque partem limites emiserunt HYGIN., p. 170), in the same way as was done in the foundation of the temple. Therefore, the direction of the axis of this temple, that is of the decumanus, was in correspondence with the day of the foundation; and therefore once that it is known, this can also be known with an astronomical calculation. On the other hand, the festivals in honour of a divinity were usually instituted to commemorate the day of the foundation of a temple dedicated to it [Once more. Please consider that the consecration/dedication of the temple is the last act of the long sequence related to the building of the temple. The festival of the temple was that of the dedication of the temple to its deity, not of the foundation, as Nissen is considering the day when the long axis of it was determined, Sparavigna]. Festus gives two very clear examples: Martias calendas matronae celebrabant, quod eo die Iunonis Lucinae aedis coli coepta erat (p. 147); Quinquatrus... Minervae autem dicatum eum diem existimant, quod eo die aedis eius in Aventino consecrata est (p. 257). Then, having determined from the orientation of the temple the day of its foundation, if on that day or in the neighboring ones the calendar places a feast, there is good probability that the god in whose honor that feast was held, was also the god to whom that temple was erected. This is the new theory of the Author [Nissen] on the orientation of the ancient temples. The bases on which it rests are very reasonable, because I [De Petra] do not find that the presupposition which establishes that

the ancients found links among the signs of the sky to the temples of the Gods on earth, can be contested. The special applications, which Nissen makes of this principle to the Greek and Italian antiquities, are demonstrated by him with good arguments. The only thing is the following, that the practical utility of his theory remains in a very narrow field. Because the astronomical aids to find the orientation of the temple needs a deep knowledge of the ancient chronology, to translate with accuracy the days and months of our calendar into the days and months of the calendars prior to the Julian reform, Roman always, and, as a desideratum, it is also requiring the complete knowledge of the ancient feasts.

On the one hand, there is the problem of chronology, and on the other, the day of the temple festival is related to the consecration/dedication of the temple, which is the final, not the initial, act of the temple's construction. Therefore, the sunrise on the day when the direction of the temple was determined on the ground has nothing to do with its festival. Then, the Nissen theory is ill-posed.

In his review of Nissen's *Das Templum, De Petra* considers nothing unreasonable in finding signs of the sky reflected in the directions of temples or cities. The problem, however, is that there is a chronological issue. There is no correspondence between the Julian calendar and the Roman lunisolar calendar, that would allow an exact correspondence between sunrise and Roman feasts. And then we do not have complete knowledge of the ancient feasts. So, what good is Nissen's theory for? Nissen seems so convinced of his thesis that he does not even consider the problem of chronology (the same can be said of Aveni and Romano). And he did not even remember that the Roman feasts, before the introduction of the Julian calendar, were like Easter today. The date of Easter changes every year, depending on the first full moon after the spring equinox. It is therefore not possible to associate a specific solar direction with Easter.

In any case, above all, the Nissen theory is ill-posed: the festival of the temple is that of the consecration/dedication, not of the "foundation" as understood by Nissen. For what is regarding the *Dies Natalis* of the towns, in Eckstein, 1979, we can find different opinions proposed by scholar. Again, the *Dies Natalis* has nothing to do with the sunrise the day of the "foundation".

When studying archeoastronomy, it is essential to go well beyond what is said in the articles and what we find in the references given therein. For example, let's pay close attention to what is the *Dies Natalis* of the towns, and the *Dies Natalis* of the temples, that is, of their consecration/dedication. Let's pay close attention to what is meant by "foundation", especially for the Romans, where we have ancient literature and several modern discussions. The Romans did not have the verb "to found", but two verbs "condere" and "deducere". The deduction of a colony occurs even when there was already an urban center, and its decumanus already determined.

Appendix – From Linderski's review

Linderski starts remembering Tages. "The founder of the disciplina Etrusca, Tages, was believed to have sprung from a furrow: "sulcis emicuit et ritum statim genti[s] extispiciumque monstravit." Or, as Cicero sneers, when the bubulcus who unearthed Tages uttered a clamor of amazement (for Tages was both a puer and a senex), a great crowd gathered from all over Etruria; the puer exaratus perorated at great length, and all his oratio, "qua haruspicinae disciplina continetur," was committed to writing". Tages was related to a bubulcus. "In 1877, in the vicinity of Piacenza in Northern Italy, a modern bubulcus, plowing a field belonging to a count, unearthed a bizarre bronze object" (Linderski, 1990). "The first scholarly study of the find appeared already in 1880; it came from the pen of Wilhelm Deecke, the leading Etruscologist in Germany, and the inheritor of the mantle of the great Karl Otfried Muller. Deecke first interpreted the object as a templum, an instrument for the observation and interpretation of celestial signs; soon, after a communication from G. Körte, he recognized its true character: a (natural size) bronze model of sheep's liver" (Linderski, 1990). "The names engraved on the model are the names of various deities, twenty-eight in all: each in his or her own "house," or sharing it with another occupant. Some important deities occupy several houses. The liver reflected the heavens. Its regions corresponded to the abodes of gods in the sky, and thus by examining the liver of a sacrificial animal the haruspex was able to establish which gods were

angry, which favorable or neutral, and what the future held” (Linderski,1990). “For the technique of the haruspex, the signs he was looking for, and the terminology, see the masterly study by C. O. Thulin, *Die etruskische Disciplin . . .* . In particular, the haruspex examined with greatest diligence the caput iecoris (= processus caudatus lobi dextrii), represented in the diagram as the triangular shape in the right lobe (cf. Cic. Div. 2. 32)” (Linderski, 1990). “The number of the marginal regions, sixteen, offers a first clue to the cosmic system of the liver: according to the unanimous testimony of the ancients, the division of the heaven into sixteen parts was an Etruscan invention, and indeed it has not been found anywhere outside the Etruscan world. In this way the Etruscans could easily establish "fulmen qua ex parte venisset" (Linderski, 1990, mentioning Cicero).

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